

Notes

Thermochemical Studies of some Copper(II) Carboxylates

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A number of copper(II) carboxylates known for subnormal magnetic moments at room temperature, with an exception of formates, have dimeric structures¹. Most of them are structurally identical consisting of binuclear inner complexes, $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{RCOO})_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_0 \text{ or } 2]^2$, where $\text{R} = \text{CH}_3, \text{C}_2\text{H}_5$, etc.

The present communication deals with the bomb calorimetric determination of enthalpies of combustion (ΔH_c) of a few copper(II) carboxylates and subsequently their standard enthalpies of formation (ΔH_f°). Some relevant mean bond dissociation energies have been estimated, viz. that of copper-oxygen (carboxylato) and copper-copper in dimeric complexes, $\bar{D}(\text{Cu}-\text{O})$ and $D(\text{Cu}-\text{Cu})$, respectively.

Experimental

The complexes were prepared by the reported procedure². ΔH_c was determined bomb calorimetrically by burning the sample in an excess oxygen and measuring the temperature rise in known quantity of water. Before commencement of the experiment, the calorimeter was standardised with certified grade benzoic acid (crystalline) and the water equivalent (W) was found out.

Results and Discussion

The enthalpies of combustion (ΔH_c) of copper(II) carboxylates have been calculated from

the relation,

$$\Delta H_c = M \times W \times \Delta t$$

where M is the formula weight of the complex, W the water equivalent of bomb calorimeter found as 10545 ± 15 joules K^{-1} and Δt the temperature rise per gram of the complex.

The standard enthalpies of formation (ΔH_f°) of the complexes are found from the relation,
 $\Delta H_f^\circ(\text{cryst.}) =$

$$\Delta H_f^\circ(\text{products, standard states}) - \Delta H_c$$

For the estimation of copper-oxygen mean bond dissociation energy, $\bar{D}(\text{Cu}-\text{O})$ in the copper(II) carboxylates, the enthalpy of formation of complex in gaseous state (ΔH_g) has been determined by the general equation,

$$\Delta H_g = \Delta H_f^\circ \text{Cu}(\text{RCOO})_2(\text{c}) + \Delta H_{\text{sub}} - \Delta H_f^\circ \text{Cu}(\text{g}) - 2 \Delta H_f^\circ \text{RCOO}(\text{g})$$

The quantities involved in the equation are: $\Delta H_f^\circ \text{Cu}(\text{RCOO})_2(\text{c})$ is the standard enthalpy of formation of the crystalline complex, ΔH_{sub} the enthalpy of sublimation of the complex, $\Delta H_f^\circ \text{Cu}(\text{g})$ the standard enthalpy of formation of gaseous metal, and $\Delta H_f^\circ \text{RCOO}(\text{g})$ the standard enthalpy of formation of carboxylate radical.

The enthalpy of sublimation values are difficult to be measured experimentally due to decomposition of the complexes at elevated temperatures. However, it is observed that these values vary little from one another for the molecules, ligands or atoms of the same type. Most of the first row transition metal chlorides have ΔH_{sub} values around $200 - 250$ kJ mol^{-1} . For copper(II) carboxylates, this value may be taken as 200 kJ mol^{-1} which is nearly the same as that of CuCl_2 ⁴. $\Delta H_f^\circ \text{Cu}(\text{g})$ and $\Delta H_f^\circ \text{RCOO}(\text{g})$ values are obtained from standard sources^{4,5}.

Table 1 shows some thermochemical data for a few copper(II) carboxylates.

Since in the above compounds carboxylates are bidentate ligands, $\bar{D}(\text{Cu}-\text{O})$ values are taken as

TABLE 1 - THERMOCHEMICAL DATA FOR SOME COPPER(II) CARBOXYLATES

Compd. (cryst.)	Δt $^\circ\text{C g}^{-1}$	ΔH_c kJ mol^{-1}	ΔH_f° kJ mol^{-1}	$\bar{D}(\text{Cu}-\text{O})$ kJ mol^{-1}	$D(\text{Cu}-\text{Cu})$ kJ mol^{-1}
$\text{Cu}(\text{HCOO})_2$	0.287 ± 0.005	-465 ± 8	-765	—	—
$\text{Cu}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2$	0.889 ± 0.003	-1702 ± 5	-887	148	100
$\text{Cu}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	0.800 ± 0.014	-1683 ± 20	-1192	—	—
$\text{Cu}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{COO})_2$	1.310 ± 0.002	-2894 ± 4	-1053	185	125

one-fourth of ΔH_g . D(Cu—Cu), the copper-copper bond dissociation energy in dimeric complexes is estimated as described in the literature⁶.

The metal-oxoligand mean bond dissociation energy is higher for copper(II) propionate than that of the acetate or the formate depending upon ligand field strength.

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Potentiometric Studies of some Trivalent Rare Earth Complexes with *p*-Sulphono-2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene Anil

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THE present communication deals with pH-metric determination of formation constants of complexes of *p*-sulphono-2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene anil with Pr^{III}, Nd^{III}, Sm^{III} and Gd^{III} using Bjerrum-Calvin^{1,2} pH-titration technique as modified by Irving and Rossotti³. The study was carried out in aqueous medium at 25, 35 and 45° at constant ionic strength.

Experimental

The Schiff base ligand *p*-sulphono-2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene anil was prepared by sulphonation of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene anil using the reported method⁴. All other chemicals were either of A.R. grade or purified before use. Rare earth metals were converted to perchlorates and were estimated by EDTA method⁵.

Concentrations of reactants used were 0.02 *M* acid, 0.1 *M* NaClO₄, 0.004 *M* ligand and 0.001 *M* metal salt. Total volume in each case was 50 ml. An ECIL 5651 digital pH-meter with combined glass electrode was used for pH measurement in titrations against standard alkali.

Results and Discussion

The \bar{n}_H values extend over the range, $0.35 < \bar{n}_H < 1.94$ which indicates a two-step deprotonation for the ligand. The proton-ligand constants, K_1^H and K_2^H correspond to the deprotonation of the phenolic hydroxyl attached to the naphthaldehyde moiety and sulphonic acid⁶ group, respectively.

\bar{n} values for Nd^{III} were in the range, $0 < \bar{n} < 2$ and for Pr^{III}, Sm^{III} and Gd^{III} it was $0 < \bar{n} < 1$. Appearance of precipitate at $\bar{n} > 1$ prevented calculation of second step stability constant for these metal ions. It was observed that with increase in temperature the metal ligand stability constant decreases.

The order of stability ($\log K_1$) was Pr^{III} < Nd^{III} > Sm^{III} > Gd^{III}. Such stability order (Table 1) is not uncommon^{7,8} in the case of lanthanides.

The values of ΔG , ΔS and ΔH for complexation reactions have been evaluated by standard expressions⁹ (Table 1). The enthalpy terms are favourable for complexation. The entropy terms for the complexes are negative and hence unfavourable and suggests that the primary hydration sphere of the interacting ions are retained to some extent.

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TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF THE COMPLEXES AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES AND THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS AT 35°

Cations	I = 0.1 <i>M</i> (NaClO ₄)		35°		45°		- ΔG kcal mol ⁻¹	- ΔH kcal mol ⁻¹	- ΔS cal K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
	log K_1	log K_2	log K_1	log K_2	log K_1	log K_2			
H ⁺	9.25	4.50	8.50	4.45	8.00	4.70			
Pr ^{III}	7.60	—	7.10	—	6.20	—	10.00	34.27	78.79
Nd ^{III}	8.05	6.20	7.80	5.40	7.00	4.20	10.99	70.83	194.29
Sm ^{III}	6.80	—	6.25	—	4.85	—	8.80	45.70	119.77
Gd ^{III}	6.10	—	5.55	—	4.15	—	7.82	47.98	130.39